

LONG-TERM CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL OUTCOMES OF ANTERIOR CERVICAL DISCECTOMY AND FUSION USING A ZERO-PROFILE ANCHORED CAGE

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INTRODUCTION. Cervical discectomy is one of the most common and rapidly growing procedures performed to quickly relieve radicular and spinal cord compression. As fusion procedures have gained widespread acceptance, efforts in research and development have focused on improving and simplifying aspects of these surgeries to enhance patient outcomes. Various devices, including allograft bone with anterior plating, polyether ether ketone (PEEK) cages with anterior plating, and other interbody fusion devices, have been utilized, yielding mixed results. Despite the numerous technical and biomechanical advancements offering diverse fusion options, the combination of cages and anterior cervical plates has increased the risk of complications such as dysphagia.

Technological advances and the discovery of new materials have led to the development of zero-profile anchored cage systems designed for stand-alone fusion, eliminating the disadvantages associated with anterior plating. The ROI-C cage (Zimmer Biomet, Austin, TX, USA) is a cervical interbody cage with integrated fixation that provides stability to the cervical spine from the early postoperative period. These implants not only offer immediate stabilization but also negate the need for anterior plating and iliac crest bone grafting. Following an initial short-term outcome study, the purpose of this study is to assess the long-term efficacy and safety of anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) using the ROI-C, with a follow-up period of up to 9 years post-surgery.

Keywords: Anterior cervical discectomy fusion, cervical disc herniation, cervical spondylosis functional scores.

METHODS

This was a prospective, multicenter study involving patients who underwent single- or multi-level anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) using ROI-C cages. From January 2018 to January 2023, 100 consecutive patients with cervical disc herniation or spondylosis causing radiculopathy were enrolled. None of the patients had undergone prior cervical spine surgery before this procedure. All patients had attempted conservative therapy, including rest, physical therapy, and/or medication, for at least six weeks before surgery. Diagnosis was made based on preoperative radiographs, computed tomography (CT) scans, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). All participants were deemed suitable candidates for ACDF.

Patients were eligible for enrollment if they were diagnosed with degenerative disc disease accompanied by symptomatic radiculopathy or myeloradiculopathy at one or two levels between C-3 and C-7, which corresponded with neural compression at the appropriate level and side, as confirmed by MRI or CT. Patients with other spinal degenerative conditions, such as stenosis or arthritis, were included, provided the primary cause of symptoms was nerve root compression. No exclusions were made based on age, sex, compensation claims, diabetes, obesity, or other medical conditions that did not contraindicate surgery in general.

Exclusion criteria included prior spine surgery at the operative levels, ossification of the posterior longitudinal ligament, significant degenerative or traumatic instability, cervical canal narrowing requiring posterior decompression in addition to anterior fusion, fractures, infections, or tumors. Each patient was fully informed about the data collection process and the objectives of the study.

Outcomes

Each patient was prospectively followed with both preoperative and postoperative assessments. Data collected included patient demographics (age and gender), intraoperative details (such as operation duration, levels operated on, types and sizes of implants, and complications), and postoperative details (length of hospital stay and time to return to work). Postoperative functional scores, radiological findings, and surgery-related complications were also documented. Clinical and radiographic evaluations were conducted at hospital discharge, at 1 and 6 months, and then annually. All patients were included in the evaluations at each follow-up point.

During follow-up, clinical and radiographic data were gathered at hospital discharge, at 6 weeks, and at 3, 6, and 12 months, with annual follow-ups thereafter. Complications were classified as implant-related, surgery-related, or general (not directly related to the implant or surgery). All patients were consistently evaluated at each time point, with a minimum follow-up period of 4 years (mean follow-up of 7.05 years, ranging from 4 to 9 years).

The primary outcome measures included the Medical Outcomes Study 36-item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36), Neck Disability Index (NDI), and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores for neck and arm pain. Patients completed questionnaires, either independently or through interviews, before surgery and at each follow-up visit. Both NDI and VAS scores were measured on a scale of 0 to 100. Odom's grading system (poor, fair, good, or excellent) was used to assess patient satisfaction with the surgery, while myelopathy was graded using the Japanese Orthopedic Association (JOA) score.

Dysphagia symptoms were evaluated by a physician, based on the patient's condition, and graded as none (no swallowing difficulties), mild (rare episodes), moderate (occasional difficulty with specific foods), or severe (frequent swallowing difficulties with most foods). The severity of pain (VAS 0–100) and the duration of dysphagia-related symptoms were also recorded.

RESULTS

A total of 100 patients (54 men and 46 women; mean age of 40.30 years, ranging from 31 to 78 years) were included in this study, and they received a total of 127 ROI-C devices. Among the patients, 65 (65%) presented with radicular pain, 15 (15%) had myelopathy, and 20 (20%) experienced both radiculopathy and myelopathy. Most patients had a history of debilitating neck and arm pain lasting more than 6 weeks that did not respond to physical therapy or anti-inflammatory medications, or they had developed new neurological deficits due to myelopathy. All patients had a minimum follow-up of 4 years and a maximum of 9 years, with a mean follow-up period of 7.05 years.

The mean surgery duration was 77.4 minutes (range: 32 to 160 minutes). Seventy-three patients (73%) were treated at one spinal level, while 27 (27%) underwent surgery at two levels.

Postoperatively, cervical collars were generally not used, except for a few patients who requested external devices for comfort. Patients were typically permitted to resume normal daily activities, including driving, 4 weeks after surgery. By 5 weeks post-surgery, they were allowed to return to all regular activities, with the exception of contact sports, on a permanent basis. Pain medications were provided as needed after surgery, but anti-inflammatory medications were avoided during the first 8 weeks. The average length of hospital stay was 1.95 days (range: 1 to 4 days).

Outcomes

Postoperative outcomes showed significant improvement immediately after surgery ($P < 0.001$) compared to preoperative baseline measures. At 4 years post-surgery, patients exhibited substantial reductions in VAS, SF-36, JOA, and NDI scores ($P < 0.05$), indicating significant improvements in pain and function [Figure 2]. According to Odom's criteria, 94% of patients rated their satisfaction with the surgery as either excellent or good, with no significant changes over the follow-up period ($P > 0.05$). Only two patients reported minor dysphagia (VAS scores of 2 and 3), which resolved within 1 and 3 months, respectively.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we prospectively assessed the safety and efficacy of the ROI-C cervical cage, an integrated fixation system, for anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF). These results extend a previous study by presenting outcomes at 4 years post-surgery. The average hospitalization was 1.95 days, and the mean surgery duration was 77.4 minutes. Patients experienced significant improvements in outcome measures immediately after surgery ($P < 0.001$), and at 4 years, they showed substantial reductions in VAS, SF-36, JOA, and NDI scores ($P < 0.05$). Using Odom's criteria, 94% of patients rated their satisfaction as excellent or good, with no significant changes throughout the follow-up period ($P > 0.05$). Minor dysphagia occurred in two patients, but it resolved quickly. By the 4-year mark, 97% of patients demonstrated successful fusion at all operated segments. Overall, clinical outcomes significantly improved at every follow-up point, showing a high interbody fusion rate and a low complication rate. These findings align with other studies evaluating the clinical efficacy of ACDF using cages with integrated fixation systems.

This is the first prospective study to objectively analyze the use of a cervical cage with an integrated fixation system for ACDF with follow-up extending up to 9 years. The results indicate that the use of this PEEK cage in ACDF is safe, supporting its use for long-term treatment. These integrated fixation systems offer a safe alternative, even over extended follow-ups.

The development of alternative stabilization devices in ACDF aims to avoid complications associated with autologous or allogenic bone grafts, such as donor site pain, infection, hematoma, iliac crest fracture, and meralgia paresthetica. Cages have been explored as potential substitutes for autografts in interbody fusion to prevent these complications. While titanium or carbon fiber cages have been widely used for cervical fusion, issues like subsidence, migration, and structural failure have been reported. PEEK, a nonabsorbable biopolymer, has been utilized in various industries, including medical devices. PEEK cages are biocompatible, radiolucent, and have an elasticity similar to bone, showing satisfactory fusion rates, although fusion may be slightly delayed compared to autograft-containing cages.

The ROI-C cage is made of PEEK Optima (radiolucent) and uses a double anchoring system to achieve intervertebral fusion. This cage is specifically designed for implantation into the

cervical disc space post-discectomy, allowing the grafting of either autologous bone or bone substitutes. The cage's curved, self-guided plating is inserted through a direct anterior approach, requiring less surgical exposure compared to traditional cervical plates or stand-alone systems with oblique-angled screws. The system is simple to use, with a minimal learning curve, and offers immediate stabilization post-implant. The double anchoring system negates the need for a postoperative collar, with the wings firmly securing the vertebral bodies and providing stability until fusion occurs.

In this study, the intervertebral height increased significantly from 5.8 ± 0.5 mm pre-surgery to 7.2 ± 0.3 mm at 1 week post-surgery and 7.5 ± 0.2 mm at 4 years ($P > 0.05$). Additionally, the cervical Cobb angle improved from $11.6^\circ \pm 3.7^\circ$ pre-surgery to $22.4^\circ \pm 3.4^\circ$ at 24 months, with no significant changes at subsequent follow-ups ($P > 0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS

Cervical arthrodesis using a cervical interbody cage with integrated fixation has proven to be a safe and effective approach for treating cervical degenerative disc disease. This system offers a unique insertion technique while ensuring successful fusion and a low incidence of postoperative complications. Larger randomized controlled trials are needed to further validate these findings.

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